

Influence of Pre-Carbonization on the Properties of PAN-based Carbon Fibers Developed by Continuous Process

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ABSTRACT

A continuous stabilization and two-stage carbonization process was used to prepare polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibers. The effect of pre-carbonization (300-550 degree C) on the final properties and microstructure of carbon fibers was measured. This study found that the pre-carbonization process affects strongly the microstructure of the resulting carbon fibers. The results of this study also showed that a suitable pre-carbonization was very conducive to improvement in tensile strength or in Young's modulus of the final carbon fibers.

Keywords: Pre-carbonization, PAN-based carbon fibers

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber is now effectively used as a reinforcing component in the preparation of light weight composite materials because of its high strength, high elastic modulus, and low density. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and its copolymers have been found to be the most suitable precursors for making high-performance carbon fibers. Modern PAN-based carbon fibers were first developed by Shindo[1] when he pyrolysed polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fiber. The mechanical properties of the final carbon fibers depend largely on the nature of precursor fibers and various process parameters applied both on stabilization[2-4] and on carbonization[5].

Our previous studies[6] presented the results of the modified PAN fibers which produced high-performance carbon fibers. In another study[7], we presented a model for the microstructure of the stabilized fibers. We have made an additional study of the dynamic mechanical properties of PAN fibers during stabilization[8]. The author also reports the effect of a continuous stabilization and carbonization on the mechanical properties of the resulting stabilized fibers and the final properties of the carbon fibers[9]. In the present study, the author reports the effect of pre-carbonization during the two-stage continuous carbonization process on the final properties of carbon fibers.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Courtelle PAN precursor (Courtaulds Ltd., U.K.), containing 6% methyl acrylate and 1% (itaconic) acid copolymer, has been used for the present studies. Each single tow of Courtelle fiber contains 6000 strands of 1.1 denier monofilament. The precursor was stabilized and carbonized by means of a continuous process, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the continuous process comprising three furnaces in our laboratory, one for stabilization, one for pre-carbonization, one for carbonization. The stabilization furnace was divided into four zones (one meter per zone) set at different temperature regions, 190, 230, 230, and 230°C. Two sets of differential speed rollers -- feed rollers and pinch rollers -- were located at the front and rear of the furnace, respectively, as shown in Figure 1. A variable feed roller speed was used to control the speeds of fibers entering zone 1, and a variable pinch roller speed was applied to remove fibers from zone 4. In this study, the feed rollers and pinch rollers were controlled at the same speed. PAN fibers passed through the furnace in 2.25 hours.

The pre-carbonization component of two-stage continuous carbonization process was carried out by passing the stabilized fibers through a ceramic reaction tube at temperatures ranging from 300°C to 550°C, increased at 50°C intervals in the first oven, and then passing these fibers through the second oven, which was set at 1300°C, as shown in Figure 1. The length of each oven was 1 meter. The speed of the take-up rollers and the pinch rollers was also the same through this two-stage process. The stabilized fibers took 30 min to pass through each of the two ovens for a total time of 60 min. An oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere was continuously passed over both ends of each furnace to maintain an inert atmosphere.

Figure 1 A schematic drawing showing the processing of carbon fibers from PAN fibers using continuous stabilization and two-stage carbonization.

A MAC X-ray diffractometer, providing Ni-filtered Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, was used to measure the crystalline related properties of the sample. The step-scan method was used to determine the d spacing and stacking size (L_c , stacking height of layer planes).

Elemental analysis was carried out with a Perkin-Elmer model 240C Elemental Analyser. The samples from the carbonization process were analysed for carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen. The oxygen content was determined by the difference between these three.

The mechanical properties of the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers were measured using an Instron tensile-testing machine at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min and a load cell of 20 g with a testing length of 2.5 cm for all fibers. In each sample, at least 25 filaments were tested, and the average value is reported.

Density was measured at 25°C according to the density gradient column method. The density column was prepared with a mixture of *n*-heptane and carbon tetrachloride so that a density gradient of about 1.2 to 1.6 g/cm³ extended from top to bottom. For the measurement of densities from 1.6 to 2.0 g/cm³ a density gradient column prepared with a mixture of carbon tetrachloride and 1,3-dibromopropan was adopted.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The molecular chains of stabilized fiber undergo a cross-linking reaction to form the carbon planes in carbon fiber. Watt and his co-workers[10, 11] studied the volatile products evolved during low temperature carbonization (below 1000°C) and tried to deduce the chemical processes that were occurring. They found that gas evolution below 700°C is due to reactions involving the ladder polymers, the decomposition of side chains, and the cross-linking of the ladder polymers. In this work we were concerned with the effect of the pre-carbonization on the physical properties of the resulting carbon fibers. During carbonization, these molecular chains of the stabilized fiber structure disappear and form the carbon basal plane in carbon fiber. A variation in dimension of the fiber is induced due to coalescence and condensation of molecular chains. Figure 2 shows the variation in diameter of pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers according to temperature during pre-carbonization. Diameter of the pre-carbonized fibers decreased very rapidly with an increase in the pre-carbonization temperature. This was due to the evolution of gas and the condensation of the molecular chains of stabilized fiber, which led to the formation of carbon basal planes. These reactions also promoted the crosslinking of ladder polymer and led to the repacking of the structure in the pre-carbonized fibers. The diameter decreased very sharply above the pre-carbonization temperature of 450°C, indicating that the crosslinking of molecular chains and the lengthening of carbon basal planes were remarkable during the pre-carbonization process.

Figure 2 Diameter of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (□) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

When all pre-carbonized fibers were carbonized up to 1300°C, the diameter of the final carbon fibers increased with increasing temperatures up to a maximum, and thereafter decreased with further increase in the pre-carbonization temperature.

Table 1 gives the results of carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen content analysis of pre-carbonized fibers after the pre-carbonization process. During pre-carbonization, the carbon content increased and nitrogen and oxygen contents decreased. The carbon content increased from 56.8wt% at the pre-carbonization temperature of 300°C to 70.6 wt% at 700°C. At the same time, the oxygen content decreased from 20.1 wt% to 9.6 wt% as the pre-carbonization temperature increased from 300 to 700°C. However, the variation of the nitrogen content showed a different behavior. The nitrogen content decreased with the pre-carbonization temperature increase from 300° to 450°C. Thereafter, the nitrogen content increased from 400 to 500°C. Above the pre-carbonization temperature of 500°C, the nitrogen content decreased again with each step of pre-carbonization temperature increase. With lower temperatures during carbonization (300-500°C), it is known that there is considerable evolution of H₂O[10, 11]. With processing wherein pre-carbonization temperatures ranged from 400 to 500°C, the carbon content increased and the oxygen content decreased very slowly, but the nitrogen content showed a sudden increase during this pre-carbonization stage. This indicates that the higher pre-carbonization temperatures broke down the molecular structure of ladder polymers and promoted the evolution of CH₄ and H₂ from this breakdown. The elimination of noncarbon species led to the lengthening and broadening of carbon basal planes from ladder polymers. The resulting compaction and loss of mass led to the decrease in the diameter of the pre-carbonized fibers.

Table 1 Carbon, nitrogen and oxygen content (wt%) of pre-carbonized fibers after the pre-carbonization process

Elemental content (wt%)	Pre-carbonization temperature (°C)									
	300	350	400	450	500	550	600	650	700	
Carbon	56.8	58.0	62.0	62.8	64.1	65.7	67.2	68.9	70.6	
Nitrogen	18.9	18.4	18.2	19.1	19.2	18.9	18.8	18.2	17.8	
Oxygen	20.1	19.7	15.4	14.8	13.7	12.6	11.5	10.6	9.6	

The variation in density of the pre-carbonized fibers and the resulting carbon fibers as a function of the pre-carbonization temperature are plotted in Figure 3. The density of pre-carbonized fibers increased with the increase in pre-carbonization temperature. This is due to the formation of carbon basal planes in the fiber during carbonization. Following pre-carbonization, the pre-carbonized fibers were carbonized again up to 1300°C to develop the final carbon fibers. The density of the resulting carbon fibers, although slightly higher for fibers pre-carbonized at 300°C and 350°C, was lower for fibers pre-carbonized at 400°C, and then increased progressively for fibers pre-carbonized up to 550°C. One reason for the lower density of fibers may be the

Figure 3 Density of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (□) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

conversion of open pores to closed pores. Due to the closure of the fiber surface, the penetration of the fiber surface into the inside structure by solvents was prevented. This resulted in a decrease in the measured density, suggesting that a rearrangement of the structure occurs around the open pores in these fibers.

The effect of the pre-carbonization process on the microstructural parameters of the resulting carbon fibers is shown in Table 3. The variation in the stacking height of layer planes (L_c) and the mean layer planes (L_c/d) of the final carbon fibers look like those of the pre-carbonized fibers. This indicates that the texture of pre-carbonized fiber affects the texture of the final carbon fibers. However, carbon fibers developed with pre-carbonization temperatures ranging from 450-550 °C had higher mean layer planes (L_c/d) than those fibers developed from 300 to 400 °C.

Table 2 Effect of pre-carbonization on d spacing and stacking height of layer planes of final carbon fibers

	Pre-carbonization temperature (°C)					
	300	350	400	450	500	550
d spacing (nm)	0.3628	0.361	0.3648	0.3597	0.3591	0.3621
Stacking height, L_c , (nm)	1.721	1.667	1.630	1.761	1.734	1.699
L_c/d	4.74	4.63	4.47	4.90	4.83	4.69

The results of the effect of pre-carbonization on the Young's modulus of the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers during the two-stage continuous carbonization process are plotted in Figure 4. Watt and his coworkers[14] found that the temperature range from 500 °C to 1000 °C induced an intermolecular reaction, evolving HCN and N_2 and leading to the lengthening and broadening of carbon basal planes from ladder polymers. This explains the increase of modulus of

Figure 4 Modulus of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (□) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

Figure 5 Tensile strength of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (□) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

the pre-carbonized fibers with increase in the pre-carbonization temperature in the current study. This study showed a very interesting phenomenon. This indicated that the modulus of the final carbon fibers developed under lower pre-carbonization temperatures was higher than that of fibers developed under higher pre-carbonization temperatures.

The progression of the variation in tensile strength of the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers are plotted as a function of pre-carbonization temperature in Figure 5. The tensile strength of the pre-carbonized fibers increased linearly with an increase in the pre-carbonization temperature above 500 °C. Raising the temperature above 450 °C promoted the formation of longer and broader carbon basal planes, which led to progressively increasing tensile strength [10, 11]. It was very interesting to note that when the pre-carbonized fibers were carbonized at 1300 °C to

develop the final carbon fibers, tensile strength tests on the final carbon fibers showed unexpected results. When the stabilized fiber was pre-carbonized at 300° and 550° C, respectively, the final carbon fibers developed from these samples had a stronger tensile strength than other carbon fibers.

In commercial production, carbon fibers undergo surface treatment, sizing and are then ready for use in applications ranging from sports apparel to aerospace. In next article, the carbon fibers will be given surface-treatment by air so that the surface properties may be studied.

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MATRIX MATERIALS
